

Enhancing Organizational Performance with Mediation of Information Technology Capability: Lessons from Human Resource Management Practices in Yemeni NGOs

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ABSTRACT

The article examines how the relationship between human resource management practices and organizational performance improvement is mediated by IT Capability in the Yemeni NGOs industry. Nongovernmental Organisations are becoming aware that human resources are an important asset that can provide sustained competitive advantages. Successful NGOs recognize the significance of the human element in organizational success and emphasize their development, satisfaction, commitment, and motivation to attain desired objectives. This quantitative research study used a correlational design. Therefore, using other quantitative methods such as descriptive, non-experimental, or quasi-experimental would be inappropriate. The methodology for this research was quantitative. This quantitative correlational study aimed to determine to what extent a relationship exists between HRM Practices and Organisational Performance Improvement. Three quantitative research instruments measured the variables: HRM Practices, Information Technology Capability (ITC), and Organisational Performance Improvement. The quantitative approach "produces results that can describe or note numerical changes in measurable characteristics of a population of interest; generalize to other similar situations; provide explanations of predictions; and explain the causal relationship. The study concludes that most Yemeni NGO employees lack motivation for their Organizational Performance, regardless of their job positions, such as senior managers/managers and CEOs/Directors. The Task Technology Fit theory supported this study and the Resource-Based View Theory. Combining these theories helped form the conceptual framework that extended the knowledge of Organisational Performance from the Human Resource Management Practices perspective

Keywords: *HRM Practices, Organizational Performance, Recruitment, Compensation, Employee Participation, Yemeni NGO, IT Capability*

Introduction

Organizational performance is widely recognized as an important – if not the most important – construct in strategic management research. Researchers also agree that organizational performance is a multidimensional construct. If not the most important, organizational performance is a necessary, complete strategic management research (Rumelt, Schendel, & Teece, 1994). Indeed, the focus on performance differentiates strategic management from other fields (Meyer, 1991); the raising of strategic management research increases understanding of organizational performance determinants and explains how managers can create a superior performance (Meyer, 1991). Therefore, to advance, the strategic management field must cumulate knowledge regarding theories that help explain organizational performance and prescribe ways

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that managers can adjust strategies to improve organizational performance (Combs et al., 2005). Researchers have different opinions of what performance is. The organizational performance continues to be a contentious issue in management research circles. Javier (2015) equates understanding of the famous 3Es; economy, efficiency, and effectiveness of a specific program or activity. According to Richard et al (2019), organizational performance encompasses three specific areas of firm outcomes; financial performance (profits, return on assets, return on investment, etc), product market performance (sales, market share, etc), and shareholder return (total shareholder return, economic value-added, etc.). Organizational performance is the organization's ability to attain its goals by using resources effectively and efficiently (Daft, 2017). It can be put organizational performance as the actual output or results of an organization as measured against its intended outcomes: goals and objectives. Understanding should not be confused with productivity; according to Ricardo (2017), productivity is a ratio depicting the volume of work completed. Performance is a broader indicator that could include productivity and quality, consistency, effectiveness, efficiency, and other factors.

Chien (2018) found five significant factors determining organizational performance: a. Leadership styles and environment, b. Job design, c. Organisational culture, d. Model of motive and e. Human resource policies. The concept of performance borders on both what has been achieved and how it has been achieved. Organizational performance can be measured in several ways (Ali Hassan et al., 2018). The most obvious way to measure what has been achieved and the approach used in many studies is by reference to key performance indicators (KPIs), which usually do with financial results (profitability) or productivity—measuring the "how" is more complicated. It has to rely extensively on qualitative assessments of organizational Capability or effectiveness (Stolfova & Fajfrlikova, 2019).

Addressing the significance of sustainability in NGOs' performance in Yemen, several scholars concluded that the recruitment process is not transparent (Nieves & Quintana, 2018). From choosing the suitable candidates to interview, arranging tests, and electing candidates to make the hiring decision, nepotism practices are prevalent in the Yemeni recruitment process or hiring an employee (Ali Hassan et al., 2008). Significant studies argued that inexperienced employees with Information Technology skills in Yemeni NGOs had made this industry inactive in many situations (Bonneyoy & Poirier, 2009; Medici, 2012; Elayah & Verkoren, 2020). In scholar and practitioner circles, organizational performance has been the most debatable topic, particularly in nongovernmental organizations. Many "commentators on human resource management have sought to establish a clear, definite link between HRM practices and organizational performance. Over the last decade, there has been considerable research on the Yemeni government and nongovernmental organizations, but the scenarios have not changed much (Alsheikh et al., 2017). Legge (2016), quoted in (Armstrong & Baron, 2017,) along with researchers such as Guest (2017), argue that research on HRM practices in Yemen is very limited to some corporate business industries. Still, the role of HRM practices on NGOs performance remains under question. Therefore, this study intends to examine how the relationship between Human Resource Management Practices (Recruitment, Compensation, Employee Participation) and organizational performance are mediated by IT Capability in the Yemeni NGOs industry.

Human Resource Practices and Organizational Performance

Across the globe, many studies have been conducted to recognize the contribution of HRs toward organizational performance. Studies done in Sweden by Schaltegger and Wagner (2016) raise a vital question on managing organizational performance. Its activities may establish a parallel organization within the company dealing with non-economic issues and Measuring non-economic aspects of performance. Epstein (2018) also indicates that the management is increasingly asking how companies can improve performance and, more specifically, how they can identify, manage and measure the drivers of improved sustainability and the systems and structures created to enhance performance measurements.

Nevertheless, Mockie (2018) researched a Scottish government analyzing performance management in the Scottish government and sustainability in government entities and non-government organizations. In their literature review, Organizational performance management could serve sustainability. It achieves its key objectives of enhancing governments' performance in attaining its policy objectives and keeping the electorate and key stakeholders satisfied (Oelberger, Fechter, & McWha-Hermann, 2017).

From the NGOs' perspective, Ramadan & Borgonovi (2015) in Italy researched performance measurement and management in a non-government organization. Their process requires a comprehensive understanding of how NGOs manage and measure performance and what performance aspects lead to successful financial performance, efficiency, and effectiveness. Whereas, in this current paper, the researcher prefers to assess further the contribution of Human Resources Management practices to NGOs' performance and sustainability (Civicus, 2011). In the African context, non-governmental organizations have played a vital role in boosting development by implementing and enhancing their policies. In this thesis, the term nongovernmental organization can be understood in its categorization, such as civil societies organizations (CSO) cover. Formal and informal structures formed by groups of individuals outside the state framework pursue a particular cause. At the same time, the term NGO is used only if it refers explicitly to registered, institutionalized nongovernmental organizations (Civicus, 2011).

According to Jaekwon and Aaron (2013), studies that have explicitly incorporated employees' work attitudes into analyses of the relationship between HRM practices and organizational performance in public sector organizations are also relatively rare. They address the mediating effects of three types of work attitude, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, and job involvement, on the relationship between HRM practices and organizational performance. Although several studies have examined the mediating effects of job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and organizational citizenship behaviour, little is known about the mediating effect of job involvement. Second, few studies have explored the mediating mechanism in public administration (see, however, Messersmith, Patel, Lepak, & Gould-Williams, 2011). Pattnaik and Rashmitab (2020) also examined the relationship between human resource (HR) practices and organizational performance. Good HR practices help create a source of competitive advantage for organizations (Huselid, 1995). Huselid, Jackson and Schuler (1997) have also explored the link between strategic HR practices and organizational objectives. According to Wernerfelt (1984), HR enables organizations to put resources to the best use and continuously improve effectiveness. Hence, HR is crucial to sustained performance (Pfeffer, 1994). Organizations should, therefore, possess a very high quality of HR competencies (Khandekar & Sharma, 2005) to fare well in a competitive world. In this knowledge-driven economy, human resources—which are rare, inimitable and flexible—play a primary and central role for organizations to acquire competitive advantage instead of the secondary and supportive role that human resources have traditionally been assigned to (LengnickHall & Lengnick-Hall, 2002). With more and more organizations increasingly recognizing the importance of human capital and knowledge management with respect to competitive success, it is inevitable to expect that HR management will be the lead driver for organizational success in the future. Sustained competitiveness of an organization is

contingent upon managing the human resources of an organization through the use of HR practices (Singh & Rao, 2017).

Recruitment and Organizational Performance

Recruitment which is the process of generating a pool of capable people to apply for employment to an organisation and selection which is the process by which managers and others use specific instruments to choose from a pool of applicants a person or persons more likely to succeed in the job(s) given management goals and legal requirements (Bratton & Gold, 2017). Recruitment and selection can play a pivotal role in shaping an organization's effectiveness and performance if organizations can acquire workers who already possess relevant knowledge, skills, and aptitudes and can make an accurate prediction regarding their future abilities. Performance improvement results from a well-functioning system and depends on effective human resource strategies that recruit and maintain a committed and motivated workforce (Al-Ahmadi, 2016).

Recruitment and selection have become ever more important as organizations increasingly regard their workforce as a source of competitive advantage. It is often claimed that the choice of workers occurs not just to replace departing employees or add to the number but rather to put in place workers who can perform at a higher level and demonstrate commitment (Ballantyne, 2019). HR's function is presented as a planned, rational activity made up of certain sequentially linked phases within a process of employee resourcing, which may be located within a more comprehensive HR management strategy. The recruitment and selection method may come in four stages: defining requirements, planning a recruitment campaign, attracting candidates, and selecting candidates (Armstrong, 2017).

Recruitment also refers to identifying, attracting, screening, shortlisting, and interviewing suitable candidates for jobs (either permanent or temporary) within an organization. Recruitment can also refer to processes involved in choosing individuals for unpaid roles. Managers, human resource generalists, and recruitment specialists may be tasked with recruitment. Still, in some cases, public-sector employment, commercial recruitment agencies, or specialist search consultancies are used to undertake parts of the process. Recruitment refers to identifying, attracting, interviewing, selecting, hiring, and onboarding employees. In other words, it involves everything from the identification of a staffing need to filling it. Depending on the size of an organization, recruitment is the responsibility of a range of workers. Larger organizations may have entire teams of recruiters, while others only a single recruiter. In tiny outfits, the hiring manager may be responsible for recruiting. In addition, many organizations outsource recruiting to outside firms. Companies almost always recruit candidates for new positions via advertisements, job boards, social media sites, etc. Many companies utilize recruiting software to more effectively and efficiently source top candidates. Regardless, recruitment typically works in conjunction with or as a part of Human Resources (Singh et al., 2012).

Also, effective recruitment and selection is central and crucial to the successful functioning of the organization as it depends on finding people with the necessary skills, expertise and qualifications to deliver the organization's strategic objectives and the ability to make a positive contribution to the values and aims of the organization, Sisson (1994). On the other hand, better recruitment and selection strategies result in improved organizational outcomes. The more effectively organizations recruit and select candidates, the more likely they are to hire and retain satisfied employees. In addition, the effectiveness of an organization's selection system can influence bottom-line business outcomes, such as productivity and financial performance. Hence, investing in developing a comprehensive and valid selection system is money well spent Hall and Torrington (1998).

As a human resource management function, recruitment is one of the activities that most critically impact an organization's performance. Recruitment and selection also have an important role in ensuring worker performance and positive organizational outcomes. It is often claimed that the selection of workers occurs not just to replace departing employees or

add to a workforce but rather aims to put in place workers who can perform at a high level and demonstrate commitment. Recruitment and selection play a pivotally important role in shaping an organization's effectiveness and performance; if work organizations can acquire workers who already possess relevant knowledge, skills and aptitudes and are also able to make an accurate prediction regarding their future abilities, recruiting and effectively selecting staff can both avoid undesirable costs, for example, those associated with high staff turnover, poor performance and dissatisfied customers and engender a mutually beneficial employment relationship characterized, wherever possible, by a high commitment on both sides. Pilbeam and Corbridge, (2006) provide a useful overview of potential positive and negative aspects, noting that: The recruitment and selection of employees is fundamental to the performance of an organization, and there are compelling reasons for getting it right. Inappropriate selection decisions reduce organizational effectiveness, invalidate reward and development strategies, are frequently unfair on the individual-recruit and can be distressing for managers who have to deal with unsuitable employees. Recruiting and selection is very important for the survival of every organization but that does not end there, new recruits need to be developed and appraised from time to time in order for them to be abreast with new trends and challenges. When employees are developed it help increase their performance and help sustain the growth of organizations. Therefore, the following hypothesis is developed:

H1: There is a significant relationship between Recruitment and Organizational performance

Compensation and Organizational Performance

Compensation is essential for both employers and employees regarding attracting, retaining, and motivating employees. Compensation & Benefits is the key differentiator for businesses looking to address concerns about the attraction and retention of employees while boosting productivity and maximizing engagement. Cash is king for most compensation plans. However, many organizations use non-cash awards, incentives, and recognition programs to supplement cash compensation and improve their total rewards programs (Hansen & Kjeldsen, 2018). Compensation is paid in hourly wages or annual salary combined with benefits such as insurance, vacation, stock options, etc. That can positively or negatively affect an employee's work performance (Shafiq et al., 2013). Compensation is providing adequate, equitable and fair remuneration to the employees. It includes job evaluation, wage and salary administration, incentives, bonuses, fringe benefits, social security measures, etc. According to BOB (2011), Compensation measuring job values, designing and maintaining pay structures, paying for performance, competence, and skill, and provides employee benefits. And compensation management is not just about money; it is also concerned with that non-financial Compensation that provides intrinsic or extrinsic motivation.

According to Cascio (2015), "Compensation includes direct cash payments and indirect payments in the form of employees benefits and incentives to motivate employees to strive for higher productivity levels". According to Milkovitch and Newman (2015) the, "Compensation is all forms of financial returns, tangible services and benefits employees receive as part of an employment relationship." The phrase "financial returns" refers to an individual's base salary, as well as short- and long-term incentives. "Tangible services and benefits" are such things as insurance, paid vacation and sick days, pension plans, and employee discounts. Someone works to give time, thoughts, and energy to the organization. As a counter-achievement, the organization must provide appropriate Compensation or Compensation to meet the needs of life themselves and their families.

Compensation plays a vital role because employees want balanced Compensation from the company and expect guaranteed welfare for themselves and their families while still actively working and reaching retirement. With proportional Compensation, employee welfare will be met, and it is hoped that employees will get satisfaction so that the organizational commitment of employees to the organization will be high (Ramzan et al., 2014). In this regard, Ivancevich (2010) states that: Compensation is the Human Resources Management function that deals with every type of reward an individual receives in exchange for performing organizational

tasks. That means Compensation in return for work done by the company in tips for employee work.

Employee compensation plays such a key role because it is critical to both employees and employers and at the heart of the employment relationship. Employees typically depend on wages, salaries, and so forth to provide a large share of their income and benefits to provide income and health security. For employers, compensation decisions influence their cost of doing business and their ability to sell at a competitive price in the product market. In addition, compensation decisions affect the employer's ability to compete for employees in the labour market (attract and retain) and their attitudes and behaviours while with the employer. Employee compensation practices differ across employment units (e.g., organizations, business units, and facilities) on several dimensions (Gerhart & Milkovich, 2019; Gerhart, Milkovich, & Murray, 2012). The employee compensation literature focuses on defining these dimensions, understanding why organizations differ on them (determinants), and assessing whether such differences have consequences for employee attitudes and behaviours and organizational effectiveness. In the following discussion, we briefly describe the basic dimensions of Compensation and summarize some of the fundamental theories used to explain the consequences of different compensation decisions. A panel of pay determinants can be found in Gerhart and Milkovich (2015).so, It can be hypothesized that:

H2: There is a significant relationship between Compensation and Organizational performance.

Employee Participation and Organizational Performance

Employee participation is considered a key element in the successful implementation of new management strategies and plays an essential role in determining the degree of job satisfaction (Harber, Mariott et al., 1991; Ardichvili, Page et al., 2013). This, in turn, increases the commitment of the employee as well as their motivation. Furthermore, Higgins (2012) argues that participation is a mental and emotional reflection that will fulfill individual and organizational goals, mainly if supported by the organization's climate (Ardichvili, Page et al., 2013). On the other hand, Brownell (2012) focuses on individual influence and defines participation as an organizational process. Individuals are involved and have an impact on relevant decisions (that affect them). Therefore, participation is an administrative mechanism, giving employees the right to make decisions and the matching amount of responsibility so that they feel aware of contributing to organizational performance. With the participation in hand, their motivation increases, which brings about both individual benefits and organizational effectiveness (Marin-garcia & Bonavia, 2008).

Employee participation began in the 1950s and 1960s as a movement for "industrial democracy" and "participative management." It has evolved into a variety of management practices that emphasize participation and decision-making among frontline employees. Over the last 30 years, these practices have been part of a larger research and organizational practice movement that has focused on workplace transformation through high involvement, high-performance, and high-commitment practices. Recent research seeking to demonstrate the relationship between HR practices and performance draws heavily on the theory and research dealing with employee involvement (Benson & Lawler, 2010). Research on employee participation began in earnest in the 1950s, but it reaches back to the work of Elton Mayo and the Hawthorne experiments of the late 1920s. Early researchers, including Argyris (1957), Likert (1961), and McGregor (1960) reacted against the legacy of Taylorism and "Scientific Management," in which managers were responsible for making decisions and workers were generally regarded as tools of production. In the post-World War II U.S., Taylorism led to tension in unionized plants and mistrust between workers and management, making it challenging to implement changes and increase productivity.

Employee Participation is generally defined as a process in which influence is shared among individuals who are otherwise hierarchically unequal. Employee participation represents the combination of task-related practices, which aim to maximize employees' sense of

involvement in their work, and human resource management practices that maximize employees' commitment to the wider organization (Bhatti & Nawab, 2011). Participatory management practice balances managers and their subordinates' involvement in information processing, decision-making, and problem-solving endeavours. Participation enhances people's sense of power and dignity, thus reducing the need to show strength through fighting management and restricting production. Involving employees in decisions and policy changes that directly affect their job while empowering employees to be more autonomous greatly improves morale. According to Singh (2019), employee participation is one of the many current forms of employee involvement in workplace decision-making. Managers are encouraged to allow a high degree of employee participation and autonomy, which are intended to increase workforce commitment and humanize the workplace to improve work performance and organizational good citizenship behaviour (Cohen, Chang & Ledford, 2017). A firm can have a high or low degree of employee participation. A high degree of involvement (deep employee involvement in decision-making) means that all categories of employees are involved in the planning process. Conversely, a low degree of involvement (shallow employee involvement in decision-making) indicates a reasonably exclusive planning process (Barringer & Bleudorn, 2019), which only involves top management. Deep employee participation in decision-making allows the influence of the frontline employees in the planning process. These are the people closest to the customer and can facilitate new product and service recognition, a central element in the entrepreneurial process (Li et al., 2016). This means that employee participation in the planning process surrounding the potential innovations may facilitate opportunity recognition throughout the organization (Kemelgor, 2012; Zivkovic et al., 2019). So, it can be stated that:

H3: There is a significant relationship between Employee Participation and Organizational performance.

IT Capability, HRM practices and Organizational Performance

Managing IT is a prospect to pinpoint the value of IT in business terms (Van Der Zee and De Jong, 2019); it involves setting the direction for strategy and enterprise-wide coordination of IT capabilities (Karimi et al., 2018). It is stated that managing IT helps to achieve FM through value propositions, a portfolio of services to deliver value, and production efficiency from the Val-IT domain's standpoint. First, IT systems help create a new value proposition to meet customer needs and extend recent offerings example, CRM applications to fulfill better customer needs and customer insights for demand projection, personalized design, and manufacturing (Mithas et al., 2012). Second, managing IT as a portfolio of services that deliver business value from IT investments; can subsequently increase IT's contribution to achieving OP (Peppard, 2013). Third, investment in IT improves the production efficiency of product quality, pricing decisions, lowering production costs, and productivity (Thatcher and Oliver, 2018). Accordingly, Tallon et al. (2017) asserted that adopting IT management practices will bring closer alignment between IT and business goals. Moreover, investment in IT is not adequate by itself to affect OP. Instead, IT management must reconfigure IT assets into resources with their strategic potential and then set them up effectively throughout the firm (Wang et al., 2015).

Many IT experts have shifted their focus on RBV to be one of the critical theoretical perspectives to answer the inquiry related to how and why IT affects OP (Karimi Mazidi et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2008; Liu et al., 2013; Pérez-López & Alegre, 2012). A more recent quantitative study conducted by Ong and Chen (2013) discussed the influence of IT capability on various constructs of OP. Their study covering 480 matched firms and secondary data from Information Week and CompStat database reveals that IT capability significantly influences all three constructs. They suggest that the significant level of firm value is higher than that of Organizational Performance, indicating that IT Capability was more related to firm value than performance. There we can assume that:

H4: IT Capability significantly mediates the relationships between HRM practices and

*Organizational Performance***Theoretical framework and Proposed Models**

This study has used the following theories as a theoretical point of view to examine the proposed research model. Notably, Resource-Based View is used as the main lens to operationalize and understand the relationship between the variables. The Resource-Based Theory (RBT), which is said to originate from Penrose 's idea (1959) of the firm as a coordinated "bundle" of resources, tackles the questions of the firm 's goals and strategic behaviour. The resource-based view (RBV) as a basis for a firm's competitive advantage lies primarily in the application of a bundle of valuable tangible or intangible resources at the firm's disposal. The theory suggests that resources are valuable when they enable a firm to enact strategies that improve efficiency and effectiveness, exploit market opportunities, and neutralize potential threats (J.Barney, 2016). RBV theory provides a powerful impact to an organization about how they can perform better than other organizations in the same market. There are the traditional notion that the managers have a significant impact on how organizations act but it is not the sole reason of how the organization can achieve better results than other organizations (Barney & Clarke, 2017). According to these authors, RBV theory says that the resources and organizational capabilities will influence the growth and performance of the organization.

Resource-Based Theory (RBT) was first put forward by Penrose (2009), who proposed a model for the effective management of firms' resources, diversification strategy, and abundant opportunities. Penrose's publication was the first to propose conceptualizing a firm as a coordinated bundle of resources to address and tackle how it can achieve its goals and strategic behaviour (Penrose, 2009; Penrose, 2009). RBT began to take shape in the 1980s. The antecedent of RBT was the Theory of the Growth of the Firm. Later, during the 1990s, Jay Barney's work was critical to the emergence of RBT and became the dominant paradigm in strategic management and strategic planning. (See Figure 1).

Figure 1: Research Model

Method*Sample and Procedures*

This quantitative research study used a correlational design. The general population of NGOs in Yemen exceeded 10,000 employees (Bureau of Labor and Statistics, 2018). The target population of interest for this study comprises individuals employees who NGOs

employ in Yemen. The designated leader of the organization were sent an email explaining the entire process for conducting the study. An approval letter from one of the organization's leaders will be obtained, prior to data being collected. The sample are NGO employees in Yemen. The reasons for choosing these categories of respondents are; first, they are mostly employees from various organizations at different levels of employment with experience. Secondly, they have been widely used in the prior literature (see for example the work of Ayers & Kaplan, 2005; Behrens, 2015; Brink, A. G., Lowe, D. I., & Victoravich, 2017; Chiu, 2002; Dalton & Radtke, 2013; Kaplan & Schultz, 2007; Mackey & Deng, 2016) as representatives for employees. In addition, the researcher is of the believe that this target population convincingly is representative of employees who may possibly observe directly or indirectly the types of improper acts relevant to whistle-blowing (Kaplan & Schultz, 2007). There are around 50 NGOs in Yemen. Among them, millennial employees from MSMEs (GIZ, WB, KfW, IFC, IFAD, UNDP, etc.) will be the sample of this study. The non-probability sampling technique uses convenience samples of NGO employees from these institutes.

Measures

All the items in the questionnaire designed for this study had been previously used and tested the constructs of Recruitment, Compensation, and employee participation by Latan, Ringle, & Jabbour, (2016). In further, the Organisational performance construct was measured through the items developed by Podsakoff and MacKenzie (2016). Since English is a universal language, it is the language adopted for use in the questionnaire for this study. All items included in this questionnaire have been measured by using a seven-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree and 7 =strongly agree).

Findings

The goodness of data was tested using Cronbach's alpha, through which the scales for internal consistency reliability were obtained. The reliability test is a method for checking a scale's internal consistency. Cronbach's alpha coefficient has been used as the indicator to check the degree of consistency. The value of Cronbach's alpha for all constructs/variables must be above 0.6. According to Nunnally (1967), Cronbach's alpha coefficient of a scale can be accepted if above 0.6 All the constructs and elements considered for the empirical study need to be substantiated through the reliability and validity measurement (Hair, Black, Babin & Anderson, 2010). Reliability and validity measures for empirical study indicate to what extent the data is processed without bias. Field (2009) defined reliability as the process of measuring an instrument that should consistently reflect towards that construct that it is measuring. The consistency of the data will ensure the entire study is accurate and correct and support the body of knowledge. According to Sekaran (2006), reliability measures the accuracy and validity of the study's measurement model assessment. (see table 1).

Table 1: Measurement Model Assessment

Constructs	Items	Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	AVE
Recruitment	RE1	0.896	0.862	0.883	0.900	0.643
	RE2	0.791				
	RE3	0.787				
	RE4	0.845				
Compensation	COM1	0.865	0.857	0.971	0.899	0.691
	COM2	0.758				
	COM3	0.901				
	COM4	0.914				
	COM5	0.864				
Employee Participation	EP1	0.763	0.914	0.919	0.936	0.745
	EP2	0.773				
	EP3	0.815				
	EP4	0.769				
	EP5	0.882				
IT Capability	ITC1	0.901	0.904	0.915	0.929	0.725
	ITC2	0.886				
	ITC3	0.909				
	ITC4	0.762				
	ITC5	0.850				
Organisational Performance	OP1	0.789	0.928	0.935	0.944	0.737
	OP2	0.914				
	OP3	0.790				
	OP4	0.855				
	OP5	0.900				

Figure 2: Measurement Model

Table 2 shows the indicator loadings, composite reliability (CR) and, Average Variance Extracted (AVE), Cronbach's Alpha of the reflective construct in this study. Hair et al, (2016) suggested loading values equal to or greater than 0.708 will be retained. It indicated a latent variable was able to explain at least 50% of the indicator's variance. All items for Compensation, Recruitment, Training, Employee Participation, Performance Appraisal, Job Security, Information Technology Capability, and Organizational Performance were retained as all the loadings are greater than 0.708. The CR was above the minimum threshold of 0.7 and the AVE was greater than 0.50. Thus, the constructs met the reliability and convergent validity requirement.

Table 2: Fornell-Larcker criterion

Constructs	COM	EP	ITC	OP	RE
Compensation	0.831				
Employee Participation	0.134	0.865			
IT Capability	0.300	0.185	0.851		
Organizational Performance	0.346	0.268	0.812	0.858	
Recruitment	0.300	0.237	0.743	0.823	0.801

Table 2 shows the results of discriminant validity by the Fornell-Larcker criterion, the bolded values represent the square root of the AVEs on the diagonals which were higher than the correlations between constructs (corresponding row and column values). This shows that compared to other constructs of the model, the constructs are strongly related to their respective indicators (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Chin, 1998), therefore suggesting a good discriminant validity (Hair, et al., 2017). Furthermore, the correlation between exogenous constructs is less than 0.85 (Awang, 2014). All AVEs have met all the conditions mentioned above.

Table 3: HTMT

Constructs	COM	EP	ITC	OP	RE
Compensation					
Employee Participation	0.137				
IT Capability	0.312	0.210			
Organisational Performance	0.354	0.284	0.846		
Recruitment	0.312	0.261	0.810	0.840	

Table 3 clearly shows that the problem of discriminant validity between reflective constructs according to the ratios of HTMT does not exist. As can be seen, the highest inter construct ratio of HTMT is 0.846. This ratio is lower than the cutoff 0.85, showing the discriminant validity for reflective constructs. In summary, the results of measurement model evaluation have shown that the model has attained the proposed satisfactory levels of constructs reliability and validity.

The second major process of SEM analysis is the structural equation model. The structural model can be represented by specifying the relationships among the constructs once the model is validated. According to (Hair et al., 2017; Ho, 2006) the structural model details the connection between the variables. Hair et al., (2017) proposed evaluating the structural model by looking at the beta (β), R^2 , and the corresponding t-values through a bootstrapping process with a resample of 5,000. Furthermore, reporting the effect sizes (f^2) as well as the predictive relevance (Q^2) is recommended. Sullivan & Feinn, (2012) argue that the p-value determines whether there is an effect but it does not show the level of the

effect. This study carried out bootstrapping method, which represents the PLS bootstrapping (T Statistics) results for the constructs which were drawn on the version PLS 3.0 (See table 4 and table 5)

Table 4: Hypothesis Testing

Hypo	Relationships	Beta	SD	t value	p-value	Decision
H1	Recruitment -> Organisational Performance	0.464	0.048	9.752	0.000	Accepted
	Compensation -> Organisational Performance	0.068	0.026	2.603	0.010	Accepted
H2	Employee Participation -> Organisational Performance	0.069	0.025	2.799	0.005	Accepted
	IT Capability -> Organisational Performance	0.434	0.046	9.461	0.000	Accepted
H4	Organisational Performance					

Note: Significant (p value= <0.05)

Table 5: Mediating Effects

Hypo	Relationships	Beta	SD	t value	p-value	Decision
H4a	Compensation -> IT Capability -> Organisational Performance	0.037	0.018	2.031	0.043	Accepted
	Employee Participation -> IT Capability -> Organisational Performance	0.002	0.013	0.102	0.919	Not Accepted
H4c	Recruitment -> IT Capability -> Organisational Performance	0.310	0.040	7.828	0.000	Accepted

Note: Significant (p value= <0.05)

Table 5 indicates the hypothesis tests. Concerning organizational learning capability, it was found that all the variables (Compensation, Recruitment, Employee Participation) predicting Organizational performances are significant. However, most of the relationships with the mediating variable, Information Technology Capability, are supported, except one relationship (Employee Participation -> IT Capability -> Organisational Performance training).

Figure 3: Structural Model

Discussion

The main objective of this study is to examine the relationship between human resource management practices and organizational performance. The study found that all the factors have significant relationships between Human Resource Management Practices and Organisational Performance. The results are in line with Rewat (2018) findings. It reveals important empirical results that contribute to clarifying the role of employee competencies in the relation between HRM practices and organizational performance. Results confirmed H1 by showing that recruitment and selection significantly influence organizational performance. This result parallels the findings of several studies, which found that effective recruitment and selection leads to competitive advantage and high performance of an organization (Chen and Cheng, 2012; Pfeffer, 1994; Storey, 2007). The results validate researchers' assumption (Naquin and Holton, 2006; Lee, 2010). H2 confirms a significant influence of training and development on employee competencies. These results support the contentions of Zumrah et al. (2013) who argue that employees who participated in training apply the new learned skills, knowledge and attitude in their everyday work and demonstrate better abilities and competencies in performing their job. The results are in line with the opinion of researchers (Cheng and Brown, 1998; Swanson, 2001).

Results of H2 and H3 suggest that Compensation and Employee participants significantly influence Organisational Performance. This result is consistent with the findings of Ayanda and Sani (2010). They assert that Compensation and training help employees develop such skills, which are important for their development and growth and are also important for the development and success of the organization as a whole. This result also supports the findings by Osman et al. (2011), who contend that an ineffectual appraisal procedure results in numerous undesirable challenges comprising stalled employee efficiency, less morale, less enthusiasm in supporting organizational values and objectives, consequently delaying the effectiveness of the organization. The results are not in line with the opinion of researchers (Young et al., 1995). These results parallel the findings of several studies that found that employee participation is positively related to employee performance, satisfaction, and

productivity (Pfeffer, 1994; Verma, 1995). The results are in line with the opinion of researchers (Ardichvili et al., 2003). Despite all these, the most recent study conducted by Subramaniam et al. (2011) on the linkage between human resource practices and organizational performance of NGOs in Yemen provided a similar result. The fourth objective of this study is to examine the mediating role of IT Capability in the relationship between Human resource management practices and organisational performance. The findings of this study support that IT capability significantly mediates the relationship between Recruitment, Compensation, Organizational Performance. Several studies are in line with these findings. Most firms under-manage their core software assets (Dutta, 2017). According to Weill and Ross (2019), IT Capability is the most important factor in generating business value from IT. Weill and Ross (2017) claim that IT Capability is essential because good IT governance pays off; IT is expensive; IT is pervasive; new information technologies bombard enterprises with new business opportunities, firms need to learn about IT value, IT value depends on more than a good technology, senior management has limited bandwidth, and leading enterprises govern IT differently.

It refers that the higher the IT capability of the employees, the higher the employee delivers performance. All in all, this study had identified a significant and robust association between IT capability and Organisational Performance. IT Capability has a great influence on performance. In the organization, IT Capability reflects an active work orientation in which an employee wishes and feels able to shape his or her work role or context. This feeling of empowerment has been proposed and found to facilitate the commitment of workers in the organization and increase task motivation manifested in four cognitions: meaning, competence, self-determination and impact (Thomas et al., 1990). According to Buckle (2013), IT Capability can be a motivational process by which an individual experiences a sense of enablement and provides an effective buffer against the adverse effects of stress. According to Vardi (2018), IT Capability is considered important because of the potential benefits that can result from it, including increased commitment, better decisions, improved quality, more innovation and increased job satisfaction

Implications

The managerial implication of this study is that customer positive feedback substitutes for Human Resource Management Practices in fostering perceptions of psychological empowerment. This result is important for practitioners. When customer feedback is perceived as positive, leaders' behaviours become less relevant to motivating employees. Managers can focus their activities on other tasks than those associated with people management to run their teams. Conversely, in the absence of perceived positive feedback from customers, HRM practices become important to develop employees' empowerment. This result means that service organizations would benefit from training their managers to have a transformational leadership style and adjust their behaviours according to the context under which employees work. This can be done through activities like coaching, development groups or regular training sessions. Finally, we believe that organizations able to train employees to focus on positive customer feedback and to develop transformational leaders will be in the best position to empower employees. Indeed, the focus on customer feedback reduces the pressure put on managers' shoulders to empower their teams and offers more agility and flexibility to firms that want to empower employees.

In the context of research methodology, structural equation modelling is recommended for future research in the die domain of employability because it allows the researcher to consider comprehensive tests of model fit, regression weights, correlation coefficients, means and variances simultaneously (Hair et al., 2016). SEM allows the researcher to estimate multiple and interrelated relationships through multiple regression equations. It represents unobserved concepts or variables in the relationships (Arambewela & Hall, 2017), and as well takes a confirmatory hypothesis testing approach to analyse structural theory predicting a phenomenon; hence, the method represents a causal approach that seeks to

examine a set of relationships between one or more independent and dependent variables (Cool, Dierickx, & Jemison, 2016).

Besides, in the context of the instalment of data collection, a questionnaire is suggested. The questionnaire has a functional capacity to measure attitudes and elicit other content from research participants (Salih, 2014). Questionnaires are a useful tool to gather survey information from a large number of participants (Kothari, 2016). It is also recommended that data collected through the survey should be tested for reliability, content and construct validity (Hair et al., 2014). Aside from the use of questionnaire as the instrument for data collection, it is also recommended that the sample population and size be broadened to capture a view of more comprehensive participants, making the outcome of the study better.

Limitations and future research

Future research is suggested to be conducted using Roy's Adaptation Model (Roy & Andrew, 2009) to highlight the different perceptions of employees from the working environment. Specifically, it is suggested to conduct research on the four types of Roy's adaptation model, namely, the physiologic mode, the self-concept mode, the role function mode, and the interdependence mode (Roy & Andrew, 2009), to improvise employees' performance. Moreover, the mediating construct in this study could be further explored as a moderator to evaluate their high and low effect on Organisational Performance.

From the perspective of methodology, it is recommended that the study be extended to use a qualitative approach and an in-depth analysis of benefits, Career growth opportunities, and work-life balance to increase Organisational Performance. Hopefully, this approach would be able to garner in-depth knowledge on the individual experiences of the employees considering the above significant predictors of Employee performance.

Moreover, there are several possibilities for future research in this area of study. Firstly, because Human Resource Management Practices are not a one size fit for every firm, it will be interesting to investigate the effect of HRM Practices on Organisational Performance in service firms. In service firms such as banks, employee task is more routine with a relatively lower level of creativity and innovation. There is a lower probability for group work and a higher level of specialization and task distinction. It is very important for research to be done in this direction to identify the most appropriate HRM practices for service firms.

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